

D5.1

HYPIEND Website

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Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
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1.0	22/03/2024	Laura Cercós, Marina Presas (EUT)	Draft version circulated to partners
1.1	15/04/2024	Laia Tolosa (HULAFE), Laureano Carpio (PROTOQSAR), Josep Ma del Bas (EUT), Chiara Baudracco (EUT), Giuliana Folco (ENCO)	Review and contributions
1.2	20/04/2024	Laura Cercós, Marina Presas (EUT)	Production of final draft
2.0	30/04/2024	Chiara Baudracco (EUT)	Final check and submission

Executive Summary

HYPIEND is a HEU funded project under the call Health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals: bridging science-policy gaps by addressing persistent scientific uncertainties (HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-03). Its main goal is to investigate the effects of multiple endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC) exposure on the function and epigenetic programming of the hypothalamus-pituitary (HP) axis to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the perinatal and pre-pubertal stages. To this aim a computational toxicology methodological framework will be built leveraging public data and state-of-the-art data analysis techniques to define EDC co-exposure patterns in the target population. The resulting patterns will be evaluated in a sequential tiered approach and the knowledge generated in preclinical models will be applied in two multi-center-controlled intervention studies in Spain, Belgium, and Poland, to minimize exposure to EDCs in mother-infant pairs and pre-pubertal children.

This deliverable explains how Eurecat (EUT), main responsible of the Task 5.1. has developed HYPIEND project website. This document describes how the HYPIEND project webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. This document summarizes the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project. Also, the data protection measures adopted within the site.

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Terminology and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EDC	Endocrine Disruptor Chemical
EU	European Union
HP	Hypothalamus Pituitary
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

HYPIEND is a five-year project aiming to understand and prevent the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis in sensitive populations.

EUT is the leader of WP5 Task 5.1 *Outreach and communication activities*, which has the objective to set up communication channels and visual materials to ensure continuous communication activities to generate awareness. Following the project plan, EUT has designed and implemented the official HYPIEND project webpage at M4, which can be found at <https://hypiend.eu>

The following sections provide an outline of the online website key features. The webpage will serve as the central hub for all project-related communication endeavours and will function as a central entry point for all public materials, including fundamental project information, projected impacts, and goals.

The webpage will undergo consistent updates, featuring outcomes, news, relevant links, and details about published papers, conferences, and exhibitions taking place throughout the project timeline. Its functionality will continue for a minimum of five years after the project conclusion.

The design of the webpage aligns with the project agreed corporate visual identity, granting users access to the HYPIEND project social media channels.

To ensure seamless browsing experiences on tablets and smartphones, the webpage has been developed with a responsive design strategy.

2. Website structure and content

The following information architecture for the HYPIEND website is proposed in the figure below. In blue you can see the pages/structure that have been created for the website launch, while, in light purple, the pages that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Further changes to the website structure may be made in the future to allocate documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

Figure 1: View of website menu structure

2.1. Homepage

It includes a slider “**Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis in sensitive populations**”.

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, its main objectives, and key outputs, as well as a section on the context.

Additionally, a section mentioning the consortium and linking to the partners page has been designed and included in the homepage. On the other hand, a section showing the latest publications of the “News & Events” page and the upcoming events was created and published through the homepage.

IN A NUTSHELL

Towards elucidating the health impacts of endocrine disrupting chemicals

Exposure to multiple Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs) interferes with the function of the endocrine system, especially during developmental stages of life.

HYPIEND is one of the first projects to study EDCs effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies. The findings will be used to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing EDC exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system in pregnant and breastfeeding women and perinatal and pre-pubertal children.

- Improve public health
- Raise consumer awareness on EDCs impacts
- Protect ecosystems and wildlife
- Shape government regulations and policies

[BUTTON – link to “About the project page”]

PROJECT PHASES

1) **Computational toxicology methodological framework:**

Leveraging public data and state-of-the-art data analysis techniques to further understand the real impact of EDC mixtures on health.

2) **Patterns evaluated in a sequential (tiered) approach:**

Cell-based screenings, Zebrafish models, placenta and blood brain barrier *in vitro*, *in silico* and *in vivo* models, and organoids-based organ-on-chip.

3) **Preclinical studies & non-invasive biomarkers:**

EDCs effects on epigenetic programming evaluated in preclinical models of perinatal window and early childhood. Non-invasive biomarkers of hypothalamic-pituitary axis disruption will be identified.

4) **Multi-centre intervention studies:**

Studies to minimise EDC exposure in pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children through innovative educational and behavioural change tools.

ALIGNED WITH EU NEEDS

Committed to protect citizens from hazardous chemicals

According to a [report from the Endocrine Society](#), since 2009 numerous international scientific and health organizations have raised concerns and took a public stance about the risks that EDCs pose for public health, and many have called for stronger regulations.

Scientific community concerns led to several actions on the European Commission to improve its regulatory regime. In 2018, the European Commission adopted the [Comprehensive European Union Framework on Endocrine Disruptors](#), the EU strategic approach on endocrine disruptors for the years to come, and in 2020 acknowledged the need for attention to EDCs and called for several specific actions, including a ban on several of these chemicals in consumer products, in the [Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#).

Moreover, in 2022, the EU Commission proposed new hazard classes under its [chemicals regulation](#), including endocrine disruption, to better protect people and the environment from hazardous chemicals.

Under these regulatory frameworks and scientific concerns, HYPIEND aims at contributing to develop new endocrine disruptor screening methods and map out new public health strategies and policies to minimise the exposure of the most vulnerable populations.

QUOTE

“Despite the current body of knowledge on endocrine disrupting chemical actions on the endocrine system, a comprehensive, holistic understanding of their impact on human health is still lacking. HYPIEND aims to understand the effects of EDC co-exposure in the hypothalamus-pituitary axis for minimizing exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the pregnancy, infancy, and pre-pubertal stage.”

- Chiara Baudracco, HYPIEND project coordinator

STAY IN TOUCH

Be part of our community of interest!

Keep updated on the project progress and be the first to know about our latest results while you connect with other experts and citizens interested in endocrine disruptors.

[BUTTON – link to “Stay in touch”]

NEWS & EVENTS

Find here the latest updates!

[CARRUSSEL OF ARTICLES + AGENDA]

[EMBED LINKEDIN WIDGET SHOWING LATEST POSTS]

MEET THE TEAM

HYPIEND Consortium

HYPIEND is a collaborative consortium coordinated by Eurecat that involves the collaboration of research institutions and companies, collectively working towards a holistic understanding of EDC adverse health effects during critical developmental stages.

This Horizon Europe project brings together epidemiologists, exposure scientists, toxicologists, endocrinologists, health care practitioners, phycologists and risk assessors to bridge science-policy gaps.

14 partners

8 European countries

[BUTTON Find out more – link to “Consortium page”]

Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors in sensitive populations

One of the first research projects to study endocrine disruptor chemicals' effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis

[FIND OUT MORE](#) [OUR TEAM](#)

IN A NUTSHELL

Towards elucidating the health impacts of endocrine disrupting chemicals

Exposure to multiple Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs) interferes with the function of the endocrine system, especially during developmental stages of life.

HYPIEND is one of the first projects to study EDCs effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies.

The findings will be used to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing EDC exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system in pregnant and breastfeeding women and perinatal and pre-pubertal children.

- ✓ Improve public health
- ✓ Raise consumer awareness on EDCs impacts
- ✓ Protect ecosystems and wildlife
- ✓ Shape government regulations and policies

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

PROJECT PHASES

A holistic approach to evaluate the effect of EDCs on the hypothalamus - pituitary axis

Computational toxicology methodological framework

Leveraging public data and state-of-the-art data analysis techniques to further understand the real impact of EDC mixtures on health.

[Find out more →](#)

Patterns evaluated in a sequential (tiered) approach

Cell-based screenings, Zebrafish models, placenta and blood brain barrier *in vitro*, *in silico* and *in vivo* models, and organoids-based organ-on-chip.

[Find out more →](#)

Preclinical studies & non-invasive biomarkers

EDCs effects on epigenetic programming evaluated in preclinical models of perinatal window and early childhood. Non-invasive biomarkers of hypothalamic-pituitary axis disruption will be identified.

[Find out more →](#)

Multi-centre intervention studies

Studies to minimise EDC exposure in pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children through innovative educational and behavioural change tools.

[Find out more →](#)

Despite the current body of knowledge on endocrine disrupting chemical actions on the endocrine system, a comprehensive, holistic understanding of their impact on human health is still lacking. HYPIEND aims to understand the effects of EDC co-exposure in the hypothalamus-pituitary axis for minimizing exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the pregnancy, infancy, and pre-pubertal stage.

Chiara Baudracco
HYPIEND project coordinator, Eurecat Technology Center

ALIGNED WITH USERS NEEDS

Committed to protect citizens from hazardous chemicals

According to a report from the Endocrine Society, since 2009 numerous international scientific and health organizations have raised concerns and took a public stance about the risks that EDCs pose for public health, and many have called for stronger regulations. Scientific community concerns led to several actions by the European Commission to improve its regulatory regime.

- Comprehensive European Union Framework on Endocrine Disruptors
- Adapted in 2018, the Comprehensive European Union Framework on Endocrine Disruptors defines the EU strategic approach on endocrine disruptors for the years to come.
- + Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
- + Classification, labelling and packaging of chemicals

Under these regulatory frameworks and scientific concerns, HYPIEND aims at contributing to develop new endocrine disruptor screening methods and map out new public health strategies and policies to minimise the exposure of the most vulnerable populations.

STAY IN TOUCH

Be part of our community of interest!

Keep updated on the project progress and be the first to know about our latest results while you connect with other experts and citizens interested in endocrine disruptors.

SUBSCRIBE

NEWS & EVENTS

Check out our latest updates

Project news

Partners from KU Leuven present HYPIEND use of organoid models in an international symposium

April 15, 2024
HYPIEND partners from KU Leuven have presented the project's use of organoid models at the "3D Organoid Modelling in Health and Disease 2024" international symposium

Read more

European consortium to study how to reduce the impact of endocrine disruptors on pregnancy and pre-puberty

March 6, 2024
HYPIEND project is studying the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hormonal system during pregnancy, the first 18 months of a baby's life and during pre-puberty

Read more

Upcoming events

- April 8-9**
International Symposium 3D Organoid Modelling in Health and Disease 2024
Leuven, Belgium
- June 13-14**
ENKORE CLUSTER MEETING
Brussels, Belgium
- September 14-21, 2025**
EUROTOX 2025
Common proposal of session with ENKORE cluster: "Knowledge gaps in Health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals"
Athens, Greece

MEET THE TEAM

HYPIEND project consortium

HYPIEND is a collaborative consortium coordinated by **Eurecat** that involves the **collaboration of research institutions and companies**, collectively working towards a holistic understanding of EDC adverse health effects during critical development stages.

This **Horizon Europe** project brings together epidemiologists, exposure scientists, toxicologists, endocrinologists, health case practitioners, phycologists and risk assessors to bridge science-policy gaps.

14

Partners

8

European Countries

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

List of partners

Funded by the European Union

The HYPIEND project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101137440. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Website menu

- About HYPIEND
- Interventional studies
- Consortium
- News & events
- ENKORE Cluster

Subscribe to our community of interest

Join HYPIEND community to be updated on the project developments, latest news and events

[SUBSCRIBE](#)

Connect with us!

2.2. About HYPIEND

2.1.1 The project

ABOUT HYPIEND

Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis in sensitive populations

The HYPIEND project investigates the effects of multiple endocrine disrupting chemicals exposure on the function and epigenetic programming of the Hypothalamus-Pituitary (HP) axis. The main goal is to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the perinatal and pre-pubertal stages.

To do that, a computational toxicology methodological framework will be built leveraging public data and state of the art data analysis techniques to define EDC co-exposure patterns in the target population.

The resulting patterns will be evaluated in a sequential (tiered) approach consisting in cell-based screenings, Danio rerio models of hypothalamus-pituitary axes, *in vitro*, *in silico* and *in vivo* models of placenta and blood brain barrier diffusion and new models of organoids-based organ-on-chip recapitulating the HP axis.

EDC effects on epigenetic programming will be evaluated in preclinical models. Whole genome DNA methylation patterns in the different models will be explored as a source of non-invasive biomarkers of HP axis disruption by EDCs.

The knowledge generated in preclinical models will be applied in two multi-centre-controlled intervention studies intended to minimize exposure to EDCs pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children.

Key data

Project execution: 1 January 2024 - 31 December 2028

Duration: 60 months

Coordinator: Eurecat Technology Centre

Budget: € 6.694.438,25

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- **Novel methodologies:** Developing prospective methodologies for identifying and reproduce realistic EDC co-exposure patterns and to assess their effects in the development and function of the HP axis, following OECD recommendations and standards for the evaluation of chemical compounds' security.

- **New scientific knowledge:** Increase knowledge into how EDCs interfere with the HP axis and find how this disruption can be detected through non-invasive screening methods.
- **Innovative strategies:** Guidelines combining behavioural-change techniques that could prove long-term life-style habits improvements and that could be easily implementable at schools and at clinician environments.
- **Multi-centric studies:** Spanning regions with different exposure profiles, and behaviour and lifestyle patterns to support adequate legislation and efficient policy actions across European countries, aiming to produce safer products for health and environment.
- **Raise awareness on EDCs risks:** Increase general awareness among citizens about EDCs, exposure sources and their potential adverse health effects they produce, particularly in terms of health impact.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

HYPIEND outcomes will include novel approach methodologies based in *in vitro* and *in silico* models, non-invasive biomarkers of HP disruption by EDC and new intervention strategies to minimize EDC exposure in sensitive population.

- **Improved public health:** By identifying and assessing the health risks associated with EDCs. This can help policymakers and healthcare professionals make informed decisions about how to reduce exposure to these chemicals and improve public health outcomes.
- **Raising consumer awareness:** HYPIEND will raise consumer awareness about the potential risks associated with EDCs, helping consumers to make more informed purchasing decisions and advocate for safer products and more restrictive regulation regarding environmental pollution.
- **Environmental protection:** EDCs have a significant impact on the environment. HYPIEND can help identify ways to reduce their environmental footprint and protect ecosystems and wildlife.
- **Regulatory action:** HYPIEND will help inform and shape government regulations and policies aimed at reducing exposure to these chemicals and protecting public health and the environment.

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

The project methodology includes a sequence of tasks aimed at defining the impact of realistic co-exposure to EDCs on the hypothalamus - pituitary axis in target life stages.

- 1) **Data analytics:** Data from public databases will be combined with computational approaches (such as the quantitative structure-activity relationship modelling technique - QSAR methodology, to reveal the relationships between the structural properties of chemical compounds and their computationally derived biological activities) to develop a knowledge base linking selected EDC exposure with health

- outcomes. Computational methodologies will be combined with data analysis to identify co-exposure patterns.
- 2) **In Silico and in vitro models:** Candidate EDC mixtures will be tested in cell-based models to define dose-response patterns and dosing for subsequent studies. Zebrafish models recapitulating HP axes will be used to select those EDC mixtures with a highest impact. Selected EDC mixtures will be tested in models of placenta and blood brain barrier and assessed in organoids and Organoids-on-chip derived from stem cells. Laboratory animals will be exposed to EDC mixtures from pregnancy to the first generation to assess the programming and cumulative effects of EDC exposure in HP axis.
 - 3) **In vivo studies:** Associations between EDCs and HP-related effect will be explored in pregnant and breastfeeding women and children in their 1000 first days and pre-pubertal stages. Human studies have been conceived as novel interventions to promote decreases in EDC exposure and to assess the cause-effect relationship.

Figure 3: Project methodology diagram

ABOUT ENDOCRINE DISRUPTORS

EDCs are chemicals that can interfere with the operation of the hormonal system, especially at critical developmental stages of life such as pregnancy, infancy, and childhood.

The [Endocrine Society](#) defines EDCs as “*an exogenous [non- natural] chemical, or mixture of chemicals, that interferes with any aspect of hormone action.*” Hormones are natural chemicals produced in cells within endocrine glands, which are located throughout the body. They allow for development, adaptation, and maintenance of bodily processes and health, play key roles in determining quality of life, and many are essential for survival, according to the report “[Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals: Threats to Human Health](#)” written by the Endocrine Society in collaboration with [IPEN](#).

In this same report, issued in February 2024, it is elucidated that due to the crucial involvement of the endocrine system in numerous vital biological and physiological processes, disruptions in any aspect of this system can result in illness or potentially fatal outcomes. Exposure to EDCs can therefore disrupt various bodily functions by interfering with the endocrine systems.

HYPIEND project will specifically **analyse EDCs impact on the hypothalamic-pituitary axis**, a structure where the central nervous system and the endocrine system converge. This system regulates hormones such as the thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), the growth hormone or oxytocin, which in turn coordinate body functions including somatic growth, lactation and coping with stress.

Where can EDCs be found?

- Pesticides
- Clothing, furniture, paints, electronics
- Food and drinking
- Food contact materials
- Plastics and plasticizers throughout the plastics life cycle
- Personal care products
- Household cleaning products
- Children products
- Industrial chemicals

NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION

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About Us

ABOUT HYPIEND

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The HYPIEND project investigates the effects of multiple endocrine disrupting chemicals exposure on the function and epigenetic programming of the Hypothalamus-Pituitary (HP) axis. The main goal is to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing its exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the perinatal and pre-pubertal stages.

To do that, a computational toxicology methodological framework will be built leveraging public data and state of the art data analysis techniques to define EDC co-exposure patterns in the target population.

The resulting patterns will be evaluated in a sequential (tiered) approach consisting in cell-based screenings, *Danio rerio* models of hypothalamus-pituitary axes, *in vitro*, *in silico* and *in vivo* models of placenta and blood brain barrier diffusion and new models of organoids-based organ-on-chip recapitulating the HP axis.

EDC effects on epigenetic programming will be evaluated in preclinical models. Whole genome DNA methylation patterns in different models will be explored as a source of non-invasive biomarkers of HP axis disruption by EDCs.

The knowledge generated in preclinical models will be applied in two multi-centre-controlled intervention studies intended to minimize exposure to EDCs pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children.

- ✓ **Project execution**
January 2024 - December 2028
- ✓ **Duration**
60 months
- ✓ **Coordinator**
Eurecat Technology Center
- ✓ **Budget**
€ 6.694.438,25

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

From novel methodologies to the deployment of innovative strategies to minimise EDCs risks

- Novel methodologies**
 Developing prospective methodologies for identifying and reproduce realistic EDC co-exposure patterns and to assess their effects in the development and function of the HP axis, following OECD recommendations and standards for the evaluation of chemical compounds' security.
- New scientific knowledge**
 Increase knowledge into how EDCs interfere with the HP axis and find how this disruption can be detected through non-invasive screening methods.
- Innovative strategies**
 Guidelines combining behavioural-change techniques that could prove long-term lifestyle habits improvements and that could be easily implementable at schools and at clinician environments.
- Multi-centric studies**
 Spanning regions with different exposure profiles, and behaviour and lifestyle patterns to support adequate legislation and efficient policy actions across European countries, aiming to produce safer products for human health and cleaner environment.
- Raise awareness on EDCs risks**
 Increase general awareness among citizens about EDCs, exposure sources and their potential adverse health effects they produce, particularly in terms of health impact.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

Improving public health and contributing to regulatory action

HYPIEND outcomes will include **novel approach methodologies based in *in vitro* and *in silico* models, non-invasive biomarkers** of hypothalamus – pituitary axis disruption by EDCs and new intervention strategies to minimize EDC exposure in sensitive populations.

– Improved public health

By identifying and assessing the health risks associated with EDCs. This can help policymakers and healthcare professionals make informed decisions about how to reduce exposure to these chemicals and improve public health outcomes.

+ Raising consumer awareness

+ Environmental protection

+ Regulatory action

METHODOLOGY

Step-by-step holistic methodology

The project methodology includes a sequence of tasks aimed at defining the impact of realistic co-exposure to EDCs on the hypothalamus – pituitary axis in target life stages

Data analytics

Data from public databases will be combined with **computational approaches** (such as QSAR methodology) to develop a knowledge base linking selected EDC exposure with health outcomes. Computational methodologies will be combined with **data analysis to identify co-exposure patterns**.

Laboratory studies

Candidate EDC mixtures will be tested in **cell-based models** to define dose-response patterns. **Zebrafish models and models of placenta and blood brain barrier** will be used, later assessed in **organoids** and **Organoids-on-chip** derived from stem cells. Laboratory animals will be exposed to EDC mixtures to assess the programming and cumulative effects of EDC exposure in HP axis.

Interventional studies

Associations between EDCs and HP-related effect will be explored in **pregnant and breastfeeding women and children** in their 1000 first days and **pre-pubertal stages**. Human studies have been conceived as novel interventions to promote decreases in EDC exposure and to assess the cause-effect relationship.

ABOUT ENDOCRINE DISRUPTORS

Endocrine disruptor chemicals interfere with the operation of the hormonal system

EDCs are chemicals that can interfere with the operation of the hormonal system, especially at critical developmental stages of life such as pregnancy, infancy, and childhood. Hormones are natural chemicals produced in cells within endocrine glands, which are located throughout the body.

EDCs are an exogenous [non- natural] chemical, or mixture of chemicals, that interferes with any aspect of hormone action.

The Endocrine Society

They allow for development, adaptation, and maintenance of bodily processes and health, play key roles in determining quality of life, and many are essential for survival, according to the report "Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals: Threats to Human Health", written by the Endocrine Society in collaboration with IPEN.

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HYPIEND project will specifically analyse EDCs impact on the hypothalamic-pituitary axis, a structure where the central nervous system and the endocrine system converge. This system regulates hormones such as the thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), the growth hormone or oxytocin, which in turn coordinate body functions including somatic growth, lactation and coping with stress.

Where can EDCs be found?

- ✓ Pesticides
- ✓ Clothing, furniture, paints, electronics
- ✓ Food and drinking
- ✓ Food contact materials
- ✓ Plastics and plasticizers throughout the plastics life cycle
- ✓ Personal care products
- ✓ Household cleaning products
- ✓ Children products (e.g. toys)
- ✓ Industrial chemicals

INTERESTED?

Keep up to date on HYPIEND project developments by subscribing to our newsletter

SUBSCRIBE

Figure 4: View of "About HYPIEND" page screenshots

2.1.2 Intervention studies

LIFESTYLE INTERVENTION STUDIES

Two European-wide intervention studies to reduce the impact of Endocrine Disruptors in sensitive populations.

HYPIEND project will conduct two European-wide clinical studies in pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children to minimise exposure to EDCs and assess the applicability of the identified biomarkers in computer-modelling and laboratory studies.

The studies will evaluate the effectiveness of a multicomponent behavioural intervention featuring workshops and harnessing a mobile app to diminish levels of exposure to EDCs in pregnant and breastfeeding women and their children up to 18 months after birth and 6-8-year-old children.

Intervention components

- **Behavioural change platform:** Mobile App providing recommendations to limit EDC exposure in everyday life through gamification.
- **Educational workshops:** Events to increase the knowledge on the hazards posed by EDCs and minimise exposure to these chemicals during critical development stages.
- **School educational programme:** Creation of a school-wide EDC-free culture with school staff and delegates with specific actions limiting the usage of hazardous chemicals in educational centres.

Intervention in the first 1000 days

Pregnant and breastfeeding women, and their offspring up to 18 months

Randomized controlled trial conducted to test the effectiveness of a multicomponent behavioural intervention carried out at healthcare centres to reduce the concentrations of different EDCs in different fluids collected from pregnant women (urine, blood, breast milk) and their offspring (urine and cord blood) at different time points. The study will also evaluate whether the intervention is able to prevent the harmful health effects associated to exposure to EDCs such as impairment in infant growth, behaviour, and neurodevelopment.

Study location: Spain, Belgium, and Poland

Participants: 810 pregnant women and their infants

[Logos partners leading study – IGTP-CERCA+ CMKP + UNILIEGE + UGR + UNIGE + KUL]

Intervention in pre-pubertal children

Children aged 6-8 years old, parents, and schools.

Two-arm cluster randomized controlled trial consisting of an intervention in primary schools to assess its effectiveness in reducing the EDC exposure levels by measuring exposure biomarkers in children's urine and prevent the advancement of puberty onset associated to

a high exposure to EDCs. The study, to be deployed during 3 years, aims also to increase parents' knowledge regarding these chemicals.

Study location: Spain & Belgium

Participants: 700 prepubertal children aged 6-8 and their parents.

[Logos partners leading study – UNILEGE + IGTP-CERCA + UNIGE +SCIENSANO]

Intervention studies

LIFESTYLE INTERVENTION STUDIES

Two European-wide intervention studies to reduce the impact of Endocrine Disruptors in sensitive populations

HYPIEND project will conduct two European-wide clinical studies in pregnant women and their infants, and pre-pubertal children to minimise exposure to EDCs and assess the applicability of the identified biomarkers in computer-modelling and laboratory studies. The studies will evaluate the effectiveness of a multicomponent behavioural intervention featuring workshops and harnessing a mobile app to diminish levels of exposure to EDCs in pregnant and breastfeeding women and their children up to 18 months after birth and 6-8-year-old children.

INTERVENTION COMPONENTS

A holistic approach to evaluate the effect of EDCs on the hypothalamus - pituitary axis

Behavioural change platform

Mobile App providing recommendations to limit EDC exposure in everyday life through gamification.

Educational workshops

Events to increase the knowledge on the hazards posed by EDCs and minimise exposure to these chemicals during critical development stages.

School educational programme

Creation of a school-wide EDC-free culture with school staff and delegates with specific actions limiting the usage of hazardous chemicals in educational centres.

INTERVENTION IN THE FIRST 1000 DAYS

Pregnant and breastfeeding women, and their offspring up to 18 months

Randomized controlled trial conducted to test the effectiveness of a **multicomponent behavioural intervention** carried out at **healthcare centres** to reduce the concentrations of different EDCs in different fluids collected from **pregnant women** (urine, blood, breast milk) and **their offspring** (urine and cord blood) at different time points.

The study will also evaluate whether the intervention is able to **prevent the harmful health effects** associated to exposure to EDCs such as impairment in infant growth, behaviour, and neurodevelopment.

- ✔ **Study location**
Spain, Belgium, and Poland
- ✔ **Participants**
810 pregnant women and their infants

INTERVENTION IN PRE-PUBERTAL CHILDREN

Children aged 6-8 years old, parents, and schools

Two-arm cluster randomized controlled trial consisting of an **intervention in primary schools** to assess its effectiveness in reducing the EDC exposure levels by measuring exposure biomarkers in children's urine and prevent the advancement of puberty onset associated to a high exposure to EDCs.

The study, to be **deployed during 3 years**, aims also to increase parents' knowledge regarding these chemicals.

- ✔ **Study location**
Spain and Poland
- ✔ **Participants**
700 prepubertal children aged 6-8 and their parents

Figure 5: View of "Intervention studies" page screenshots

2.3. Consortium

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. This page includes a first section with a brief description of the consortium, followed by a portfolio with the logos of the different partners, leading to a specific page per partners with their contact details.

HYPIEND is a multidisciplinary project executed thanks to a fruitful collaboration of 14 partners from 8 European countries.

The consortium, coordinated by Eurecat, is formed by technology centres, universities, research institutes and hospitals, and companies.

Eurecat

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

Eurecat brings together the expertise of more than 700 professionals who generate a volume of income of 55 M € per year. Serving two thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in more than 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value and has 200 patents and 10 technology companies.

Contribution to HYPIEND

Eurecat oversees the coordination of the project through its Nutrition& Health and Omics Technology Units, bringing high-level and scientific infrastructure equipped with leading tools and technologies in the fields of metabolomics, proteomics, transcriptomics, and genomics to carry out a preclinical study on the effects of endocrine disruptors. In addition, Eurecat will provide its expertise in the development of behavioural change digital tools, as well as project management and communication activities.

Radboud University

Radboud Universiteit

Radboud University is one of the best traditional, general universities of the Netherlands and its research is of a high academic quality, characterised by integrity and academic freedom. Located in Nijmegen. The university works to make a significant impact on a regional and an international level. Furthermore, Radboud University holds a wide range of disciplines, enhancing

interdisciplinary collaborations, and works closely with the Radboud University Medical Center.

Contribution to HYPIEND

Radboud University is in charge of testing selected EDC mixtures using zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) as preclinical model and determining the impact of those mixtures on the hypothalamus-pituitary gland-axes. EDC effects will be determined in larvae, juvenile and adult fish using transgenic zebrafish models, behavioural assays and gene expression of stress, reproduction and thyroid axes marker genes.

Germans Trias i Pujol Research Institute

The Germans Trias i Pujol Research Institute (IGTP) is a public research centre located in Badalona, Catalonia. Its main objective is to increase scientific knowledge to transform it into solutions and improve the health and medical care of patients and the community.

The Institute is associated with one of the major university hospitals in the Barcelona area, the [Germans Trias i Pujol Hospital](#), and, as part of the Can Ruti biomedical campus, coordinates the management and scientific strategy of the campus. IGTP is a [CERCA centre](#) and is also accredited as a centre of excellence by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII).

Contribution to HYPIEND

Germans Trias i Pujol Research Institute (IGTP) is in charge of the interventional studies to modulate EDC exposure in sensitive populations (1000 days of early life and pre-puberty children). To do that, IGTP will assess the effectiveness of multicomponent strategies, the performance of biomarkers and evaluate if HYPIEND interventions are able to prevent some of the harmful health effects related to Hypothalamus Pituitary disruption.

Sciensano

Sciensano is a public Belgian research institution that builds on the more than 100 years of scientific expertise from the former Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Centre (CODA-CERVA) and the ex-Scientific Institute of Public Health (WIV-ISP).

Sciensano can count on more than 900 staff members who are committed to human and animal health every day. Sciensano's strength and uniqueness lie within the holistic and multidisciplinary approach to health. In particular, Sciensano combines different research perspectives within the framework of the "One health" concept, focussed on the interconnection between human and animal health and their environment.

Contribution to HYPIEND

Sciensano is involved in the interventional study work in the HYPIEND project. In particular, Sciensano will participate in the development and implementation of the study in prepubertal

children in relation to EDCs and will perform human risk assessment for the exposure to EDCs.

KTH ROYAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

Since 1827, KTH has grown to become an international leading technical university. As the largest institution in Sweden for technical education and research, KTH bring together students, researchers, and educators worldwide. Activities are grounded in a strong tradition of advancing science and innovation, focusing on contributing to sustainable societal development. With a continuously expanding network of industry partners, societal stakeholders, and leading universities, KTH is driving the development of sustainable solutions to several of our time's greatest challenges, such as climate change, food and water security, future energy supply, and improved quality of life.

Contribution to HYPIEND

KTH is leading the charge in utilizing systems biology and artificial intelligence to translate biomarker discoveries from preclinical models to human studies, ensuring a comprehensive approach to data analysis, modeling, and the management of the project's extensive data requirements across its duration.

KU Leuven

KU Leuven boasts a rich tradition of education and research that dates back six centuries. The university's basic research orientation is fundamental research, while also remaining open to contemporary cultural, economic and industrial realities, as well as to the community's needs and expectations.

As the largest university in Belgium in terms of research funding and expenditure, KU Leuven conducts fundamental and applied research in all academic disciplines with a clear international orientation. In the Times Higher Education ranking, KU Leuven is the 14th European university, as well as the most innovative institution in Europe according to Reuters World Top 100.

Contribution to HYPIEND

KU Leuven will contribute to HYPIEND, delivering beyond state-of-the-art organoid/organ(oid)-on-chip (OoC) models of the endocrine axis to study the impact of EDCs; and running a multinational trial to evaluate the effectiveness of a behavioural intervention to reduce the levels of EDC in pregnant and breastfeeding women, as well as in their offspring up to 18 months after birth.

University of Granada

The University of Granada (UGR) is one of the largest and most important universities in Spain, with over 56,000 undergraduate and postgraduate students and more than 6,000 members of staff. The UGR is also internationally renowned for its excellence and ranked among the top Spanish universities, and it is firmly committed to its participation in the calls of the Framework Programme of the European Union. For Horizon 2020, the UGR obtained a total of 121 projects with total funding around €29,4 million. For the current Framework Programme, Horizon Europe, the UGR has obtained 57 projects, so far, with total funding around €16 million.

Contribution to HYPIEND

UGR will participate in the intervention study in the first 1000 days by recruiting pregnant women and carrying out the follow up of the mothers and their infants. UGR will be also responsible of the analysis of EDCs in breast milk samples collected as part of the project. UGR has an important expertise and scientific infrastructure in the field of analytical toxicology.

Centre of Postgraduate Medical Education (CMKP/CPME)

The Centre of Postgraduate Medical Education (CMKP/CPME) is an independent public institution established over 50 years ago. It plays a fundamental role in the system of postgraduate medical education in Poland, launching nearly 1400 courses each year for over 40,000 trainees, mostly medical doctors. CPME conducts teaching and scholarly activities in nearly 90 establishments located in Warsaw and its vicinity. In addition to scholarly activities, CPME's objectives include initiating and carrying out research activities, developing and updating specialty curricula, accrediting units providing specialty training, conducting proceedings for recognition of qualifications for medical specialties, and maintaining registers of specializing doctors and training bodies.

Contribution to HYPIEND

CMKP conducts the intervention study in the first 1000 days in Poland by recruiting pregnant women, introducing a multicomponent behavioural intervention to reduce the exposure to EDCs and carrying out the follow up of the mothers and their infants.

The HYPIEND Project will be conducted collaboratively by the 2nd Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology located in [Warsaw Institute of Women's Health](#), alongside the CPME Department of Lifestyle Medicine at the School of Public Health.

ProtoQSAR

[ProtoQSAR](#), is a Spanish company with more than a decade of experience in chemical design and development, offering a wide range of specialized services.

The expertise extends to crafting small molecules, peptides, nanomaterials, and mixtures, alongside compound reprofiling and virtual screening. Leveraging advanced Artificial Intelligence in chemoinformatics and structural bioinformatics, ProtoQSAR excels in QSAR models, molecular docking, pharmacophore modeling, and more. Renowned in chemistry, regulatory toxicology, and compound discovery, ProtoQSAR serves diverse sectors like biotech, pharma, cosmetics, and agrifood. The extensive contributions include active involvement in over 10 international research initiatives, 25+ projects, and a rich portfolio of 80+ publications.

Contribution to HYPIEND

ProtoQSAR's role in the project will involve employing computational techniques to analyze endocrine disruption compounds. The company will gather comprehensive data and create a knowledge base crucial for characterizing mixtures and assessing their impact on endocrine disruption. Through advanced computational methods, ProtoQSAR aims to provide valuable insights that will enhance understanding and evaluation processes in this domain.

ENCO

ENCO is an innovation and research-consulting SME based in Naples, active since 1987. Originally specialized in business consulting and industrial engineering, it has expanded its range of activities, becoming an experienced advisor for both private business and public authorities involved in territorial development. The company participates in national and

international R&D&I projects as a facilitator for business, product, technology, and process innovation in different areas, including the bioeconomy, energy, environmental management, the agri-food sector, logistics, and health. The company has a long track record participating in EU-funded projects.

Contribution to HYPIEND

ENCO is responsible for HYPIEND IPR management, dissemination, and exploitation activities. ENCO also leads the creation of a permanent policy hub for 'Living and working in a health-promoting environment'.

Hospital Universitario La Fe (HULAFE)

HULAFE is a non-profit organisation that carries out the scientific and research policy of the Hospital Universitario I Politécnico "La Fe" (Valencia).

The research of excellence carried out at HULAFE is patient-oriented and was accredited as a "Health Research Institute" by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation in 2009. HULAFE offers scientific and technological services and has more than 10,000 m² of clinical and research laboratories to undertake research programmes based on state-of-the-art biomedical science, which aim to promote our several priority research areas. HULAFE comprises multidisciplinary and complementary research groups with consolidated expertise biomedical and clinical research.

Contribution to HYPIEND

HULAFE is in charge of the pre-screening of compounds using different in vitro models to select different mixtures of endocrine disruptors through the Experimental Hepatology Unit. The Experimental Hepatology Unit has a renowned international prestige in the development and use of different cellular models and has also developed a high-content imaging screening (HCS) by using multiparametric approaches. The group has been a member and coordinator of different EU-funded related to xenobiotic-induced toxicity.

University of Liege – EQUALE Unit

The University of Liège (ULiège), founded in 1817, is the largest French-speaking public university in Belgium. It welcomes 28,000 students and more than 5,600 employees in 11 faculties representing the humanities, health sciences, sciences and technology. ULiège has strong expertise in the exploitation of research through the management of patents and the creation of spin-off companies and collaborates with more than 1,000 teaching and research institutions around the world. It is strengthening its research centres in areas such as biotechnology, life sciences and medical sciences (human and veterinary), agro-bio tech, space sciences, engineering and the environment.

Contribution to HYPIEND

ULiège will participate with the EQUALE Unit in the intervention study in prepubertal children by recruiting schools and children with parents' agreement, implementing a multicomponent behavioural intervention at the school and family levels and carrying out the follow up of the change of behaviors.

The EQUALE "Evaluation et qualité de l'enseignement" research unit develops researches that contribute to improving the quality of teaching and its actors.

University of Geneva

**UNIVERSITÉ
DE GENÈVE**

FACULTY OF PSYCHOLOGY
AND EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES

Geneva University (UNIGE) is the second biggest university in Switzerland and was founded in 1559. UNIGE conducts cutting-edge research and provides teaching to students in sciences, medicine, humanities, social sciences, economics and management, law, theology, psychology and educational

sciences, translation and interpreting.

Contribution to HYPIEND

UNIGE is in charge of the behaviour change aspects of the project. For the two intervention studies with pre-pubertal children and during the 1,000 first days of early life, UNIGE will provide its expertise in behavioural sciences for the content of the interventions through workshops and digital tools.

King's College of London

The Faculty of Life Sciences and Medicine at King's College London (KCL) is one of the largest and most successful centres for research and education in the UK, with extensive global partnerships.

It is strategically aligned with King's Health Partners, bringing together academics and clinicians who are committed to ensuring efficient translation and adoption of research innovation into daily clinical practice. The faculty is ranked 14th in the world for Life Sciences & Medicine, 17th in the world for Pharmacy and Pharmacology and 16th in the world for Anatomy and Physiology (QS World Rankings 2022); and 13th for Clinical, Pre-Clinical and Health (Times Higher Education World Rankings 2024).

Contribution to HYPIEND

KCL is leading one of the discovery science aspects of the project – using preclinical models to explore how endocrine disrupting chemical traverse important biological barriers such as the placenta and the blood-brain barrier. KCL has strong expertise in Molecular Endocrinology and Women and Children's health, which brings an important toolkit of expertise to the project.

Our Team

PARTNERS

HYPIEND project consortium

HYPIEND is a multidisciplinary project executed thanks to a fruitful collaboration of **14 partners** from **8 European countries**.

The consortium, coordinated by Eurecat, is formed by technology centres, universities, research institutes and hospitals, and companies.

- 1**
RTO
- 2**
Companies
- 8**
Universities
- 3**
Hospitals

Eurecat – COORDINATOR

Radboud University

Germans Tiras i Pujol Research Institute

Sciensano

KTH ROYAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

KU Leuven

Figure 6: View of "Consortium" page

Figure 7: Example of partner page

2.4. News & Events

This page shows articles related to HYPIEND project advances and results, as well as general assembly meetings or articles written by partners on project topics.

It also includes an agenda announcing events that HYPIEND consortium is organising or attending/participating (conferences, meetings, fairs, congresses, and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

Within this page, project events such as the final conference, webinars and workshops will be announced and promoted. Each event will count with a specific page with the information on the event, agenda, and form to register. After the event, the presentations and documents delivered during the event will be made available for download through the page, as well as video recording of the sessions.

News & Events

HYPIEND UPDATES

The latest news & events of the HYPIEND project

- April 8-9**
International Symposium 3D Organ modelling in Health and Disease 2024
Leuven, Belgium
- June 13-14**
ENKORE CLUSTER MEETING
Brussels, Belgium
- September 14-21, 2025**
EUROTOX 2025
 Common proposal of session with ENKORE cluster: "Knowledge gaps in Health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals"
Athens, Greece

NEWS

Find here information about dissemination actions, including conferences and congresses

[VIEW ALL](#)
[CONFERENCES](#)
[PRESS RELEASE](#)
[PROJECT MEETING](#)

Partners from KU Leuven present HYPIEND use of organoid models in an international symposium

April 15, 2024

HYPIEND partners from KU Leuven have presented the project's use of organoid models at the "3D Organ modelling in Health and Disease 2024" international symposium

[READ ARTICLE →](#)

European consortium to study how to reduce the impact of endocrine disruptors on pregnancy and pre-puberty

March 6, 2024

HYPIEND project is studying the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hormonal system during pregnancy, the first 18 months of a baby's life and during pre-puberty

[READ ARTICLE →](#)

HYPIEND project kicks-off!

January 31, 2024

The HYPIEND project has kicked off on January 2024 in Barcelona with the objective of understanding and preventing the impact of Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDC).

[READ ARTICLE →](#)

Figure 8: View of "News&Events" page screenshots

2.5. Resources

This page will gather all public materials of the project, including visual materials, videos, public deliverables, scientific publications, and media features. Specific pages for each type of content will be created depending on the number of results for a correct visualisation.

Main outcomes:

- **Media impacts:** main articles featuring HYPIEND project in generalist and specialised media outlets.
- **Deliverables:** all public reports will be published on this website for in-depth access to project outputs.
- **Promotional materials:** project promotional materials produced (rollups, info sheets, posters, etc).
- **Scientific publications:** all scientific articles related to the project research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.
- **Audio visual materials:** a set of short videos will be produced to present HYPIEND concept and impacts.

Media impacts

MEDIA IMPACTS

HYPIEND in the news

See below a selection of articles featuring HYPIEND in print and online media outlets, as well as key impacts in national TVs and radios.

Do you want to interview one of our researchers about this project?

[Contact us!](#)

Figure 9: View of "Media impacts" page

2.6. ENKORE cluster

The HYPIEND project is part of the ENKORE Cluster: “ENdocrine disrupting chemicals and Knowledge On health-Related Effects”, aiming at optimising synergies and increasing the impact of the 5 projects funded under the Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-03 *Health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals: bridging science-policy gaps by addressing persistent scientific uncertainties*.

Within the ENKORE Cluster framework, the participating projects share a common goal to extend their reach beyond individual project boundaries, thereby magnifying their collective impact. By leveraging the collaborative strength of the cluster, these initiatives aspire to disseminate cutting-edge research insights into the effects of EDCs on human health and to forge crucial connections between scientific knowledge and policymaking processes.

CLUSTER PROJECTS

EDC- MASLD

EDC – MASLD

CORDIS LINK: [Investigation of endocrine-disrupting chemicals as contributors to progression of metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease | EDC-](#)

[MASLD | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

EDC-MASLD will investigate the impact of environmental exposure to EDCs on the internal exposome (metabolome, gut microbiome, epigenome, proteome, immunome) and the degree of liver damage in MASLD - the condition of excessive accumulation of liver fat unrelated to alcohol intake, ranging from simple steatosis to metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis. EDC-MASLD is particularly focused on interactions between EDC exposure, sex, genotype, diet, socioeconomic and lifestyle factors, via the data and biosamples available in the unique European NAFLD Registry, comprising over 9,000 patients with histologically characterised MASLD.

ENDOMIX,

CORDIS LINK: [Understanding how endocrine disruptors and chemical mixtures of concern target the immune system to trigger or perpetuate disease | ENDOMIX | Project | Fact sheet |](#)

[HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

The ENDOMIX project addresses the urgent need to understand the true impact of endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) on human health to inform regulators and advise citizens. ENDOMIX will tackle this challenge by revealing associations and causality between EDCs and adverse health outcomes by focusing on exposure to multiple EDCs during life course including windows of susceptibility and making use of already existing robust data from multiple European cohorts. The knowledge generated will be disseminated to the scientific community, provide a thorough new evidence base for policy making and will reach citizens to raise awareness about the risks of EDC exposure.

NEMESIS

CORDIS LINK: [Novel Effect biomarkers for METabolic disruptorS: evidence on health Impacts to answer science and policy needS | NEMESIS | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

NEMESIS addresses the adverse metabolic effects of EDCs through a multidisciplinary approach and responds to unmet regulatory needs regarding EDCs. NEMESIS aims to elucidate the mechanisms and dose-dependency of metabolic disruption by EDCs and their mixtures in liver and pancreas as well as their effects on gut microbiota through in silico, in vitro, in vivo, epidemiological and systems

biology approaches. The consortium will support risk assessment by improving regulatory testing guidelines by incorporating metabolic endpoints and developing AOPs and IATAs. Engagement with citizens and stakeholders ensures effective risk communication and maximizes the impact of NEMESIS on policy development.

MERLON

CORDIS LINK: [Merging scientific Evidence with Regulatory practices and Leveraging identification Of endocrine disruptors using New approach methodologies | MERLON | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

The MERLON project aims to improve our knowledge on how EDC exposures at critical life stages impacts sex development and reproductive health, with a goal to improve on available tools for EDC identification. It brings together world-leading experts in endocrinology, chemical safety assessment, developmental and molecular biology, epidemiology, toxicogenomics, toxicokinetics modelling, regulatory toxicology, and psychology to tackle to investigate EDC-mediated effects on sexual development, providing human data on the role of EDC exposure during fetal development and changes in mini-puberty, connecting to puberty, reproductive function, and gender incongruence.

CORDIS LINK: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137440>

HYPIEND is one of the first projects to study EDCs effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies.

The findings will be used to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing EDC exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system in pregnant and breastfeeding women and perinatal and pre-pubertal children.

PROMOTION CLUSTER NEWSLETTER

Section to be developed:

STAY IN TOUCH

Are you interested in the ENKORE cluster?

Subscribe now to the cluster newsletter to receive the latest news and research results on the health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals from five Horizon Europe projects.

[BUTTON Subscribe – Newsletter subscription link]

CLUSTER EVENTS

Section to be developed announcing and summarizing the outcomes of Cluster Events.

CLUSTER MATERIALS

Section including access to cluster materials (newsletters, brochures, etc.).

ENKORE Cluster

ENKORE CLUSTER

Establishing synergies for broader impact with sister projects

The HYPIEND project is part of the ENKORE Cluster: "Endocrine disrupting chemicals and Knowledge On health-Related Effects", aiming at optimising synergies and increasing the impact of the 5 projects funded under the Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-03 Health impacts of endocrine-disrupting chemicals: bridging science-policy gaps by addressing persistent scientific uncertainties.

Within the ENKORE Cluster framework, the participating projects share a common goal to extend their reach beyond individual project boundaries, thereby magnifying their collective impact. By leveraging the collaborative strength of the cluster, these initiatives aspire to disseminate cutting-edge research insights into the effects of EDCs on human health and to forge crucial connections between scientific knowledge and policymaking processes.

SISTER PROJECTS

5 EU projects working on assessing the health impacts of endocrine disrupting chemicals

EDC - MASLD

EDC-MASLD will investigate the impact of environmental exposure to EDCs on the internal exposome (metabolome, gut microbiome, epigenome, proteome, immunome) and the degree of liver damage in MASLD - the condition of excessive accumulation of liver fat unrelated to alcohol intake, ranging from simple steatosis to metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis. EDC-MASLD is particularly focused on interactions between EDC exposure, sex, genotype, diet, socioeconomic and lifestyle factors, via the data and biosamples available in the unique European NAFLD Registry, comprising over 9,000 patients with histologically characterised MASLD.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

ENDOMIX

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[FIND OUT MORE](#)

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[FIND OUT MORE](#)

MERLON

The MERLON project aims to improve our knowledge on how EDC exposures at critical life stages impacts sex development and reproductive health, with a goal to improve on available tools for EDC identification. It brings together world-leading experts in endocrinology, chemical safety assessment, developmental and molecular biology, epidemiology, toxicogenomics, toxicokinetics modelling, regulatory toxicology, and psychology to tackle to investigate EDC-mediated effects on sexual development, providing human data on the role of EDC exposure during fetal development and changes in mini-puberty, connecting to puberty, reproductive function, and gender incongruence.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

HYPIEND

HYPIEND is one of the first projects to study EDCs effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies. The findings will be used to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing EDC exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system in pregnant and breastfeeding women and perinatal and pre-pubertal children.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

Figure 10: View of "ENKORE cluster" page

2.7. Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@hypiend.eu has been created and is shown on the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email to manage all information requests received.

Figure 11: View of "Contact" page screenshot

3. Layout

The HYPIEND website menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the site.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- HYPIEND logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Access to Social Media platforms (LinkedIN, Instagram & YouTube - when created).
- Access to Sharepoint

Footer

- EU logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase “*The HYPIEND project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101137440. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them*”.
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Link to newsletter subscription
- Contact info

Figure 12: View of HYPIEND website header

Figure 13: View of HYPIEND website footer

4. Managing and updating policy

The development of the website has been led by EUT, drawing on insights and contributions from all consortium partners.

A continuous process of updates is planned for the HYPIEND project website. New content and information will be integrated each time a new dissemination initiative is executed, significant results are achieved, or there are noteworthy developments that warrant publication. This dynamic approach ensures that the website remains an updated and comprehensive resource for project-related information and progress updates.

5. Analytics

The HYPIEND has installed Matomo in the website's backend to systematically track website traffic and collect periodic reports on the site's performance. This enables the project team to gain insights into visitor interactions and overall webpage effectiveness. Unlike Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services and third parties.

Figure 14: View of Matomo Analytics dashboard of HYPIEND website

6. Site hosting, installation and management

EUT has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

On the other hand, EUT is the partner responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end adding content and updating it regularly. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that HYPIEND website is well positioned in the browsers. The website will be maintained at least five years after the projects' end.

7. Data protection

HYPIEND website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD “Guidelines on the Use of Cookies”, compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click “I accept”. In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.hypiend.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

The users may revise their cookies’ selection at any time as the Cookies Setting Banner is available at the bottom right part of the page. The website also includes specific pages for allocating the privacy policy (<https://www.hypiend.eu/privacy-policy>), the cookies policy (<https://www.hypiend.eu/cookies-policy>) and the legal notice (<https://www.hypiend.eu/legal-warning/>). See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy texts on Annex 5.1-5.5.

The webpage includes two forms gathering personal data from users: a contact form to manage user’s queries and an external sign-up form for users to subscribe to HYPIEND Community of Interest (for more information see 3.10.2). For both forms EUT is the data controller. The data of the contact form will be transferred to partners involved in the project to better reply to the requests, while the users’ data of the community of interest will not be disclosed to third-parties and will be processed by Mailchimp.

The website will also include specific forms to manage the registration of interest users to project events. The data included in these forms will be disclosed with the organising partner with the solely objective to register the users to the event and be able, afterwards, to send event materials to attendees.

8. Website accessibility

As part of the HYPIEND’s website design and publication, EUT applied [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\)](#). The aim was to avoid barriers that may affect some users, with special attention to those that hinder the use of the website with users with different disabilities. These guidelines were followed, for example, when designing the web structure (“Guideline 2.4 – Navigable Provide ways to help users navigate, find content, and determine where they are”); when choosing colours (“Guideline 1.4 – Distinguishable. Make it easier for users to see and hear content including separating foreground from background”); or when using alternative texts (“Guideline 1.1 – Text Alternatives. Provide text alternatives for any

non-text content so that it can be changed into other forms people need, such as large print, braille, speech, symbols or simpler language”).

9. Website KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of HYPIEND Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the website performance. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

As we expect to not be able to record all website analytics due to the new AEPD regulation on third-party cookies, such the ones used for getting analytics on website performance (see more information on section 7. Data Protection), KPIs related to the website activity have been designed and established with caution taking the regulation into account.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M60
Website	Number of website visits	Website Analytics	>5,000
	Number of pages viewed		>10,000
	Number of users		>2,000
	Updates per year		3 updates / year
	Number of informative blog posts		20 blog posts published

The progress of KPIs until the end of the project will be reported. In addition, to facilitate the reporting, an Excel file has been prepared to record the monthly progress of KPIs.

The file is stored in the shared WP5 folder (accessible by all partners) and includes the following items.

KPIs HYPIEND Digital Channels	jan 2024	Feb-24	Mar-24	apr-2024
HYPIEND Website (MATOMO Analytics)				
# Web Visits	NA	NA	NA	
Avg. session time	NA	NA	NA	
# Pages Viewed	NA	NA	NA	
# Actions / Session	NA	NA	NA	
# Users	NA	NA	NA	

Figure 15: View of file for tracking HYPIEND website monthly analytics.

10. Annex

10.1 Privacy Policy

Preliminary information

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT considers your personal information is very important. We therefore process it confidentially and securely. We are committed to ensuring the privacy of personal data at all times and not to collect unnecessary information.

You do not need to previously sign up in order to access our website. If you require any further information, you can contact us through the form available on our website, providing you agree with our privacy policy, which you must accept in order to record your express consent to the data processing for the specified purposes.

Pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and Act 3/2018 of 5 December on the protection of personal data and guarantee of digital rights, we provide you with information about the processing of your data through this Privacy Policy.

Who processes the data?

Identity: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (hereinafter referred to as “Eurecat“)

Tax Identification Code (NIF): G66210345

Registered office: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 – 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Legal department email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone number: + 34 93 238 14 00

Data Protection Officer

Email address of the Data Protection Officer: dpo@eurecat.org

What data do we collect, for what purposes and for how long do we store them?

DATA PROCESSING PURPOSE AND LEGAL BASIS	STORAGE PERIOD
<p>Contact form</p> <p>To respond to requests and enquiries made by the user, the legal basis of the processing being the data subject’s express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR.</p>	<p>The data collected will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in any case, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations</p>

<p>Sending informative messages about the company and the Newsletter</p>	<p>To subscribe to information, promotions and offers of the company, the legal basis for the processing being the data subject's express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR.</p>	<p>The data will be stored for the period the data subject has subscribed to the Newsletter or until he/she exercises the right to object to or erase the data. However, they may be stored in order to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose</p>
<p>Email management</p>	<p>To respond to the enquiries received and to manage the commercial or professional relationship, the legal basis being the contractual relationship between the Data Controller and the data subject, pursuant to Article 6.1.b) of the GDPR</p>	<p>The data collected will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in all cases, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations</p>
<p>Activities, conferences and events</p>	<p>To manage the registration to take part in activities, conferences or events. The data will be processed for such purpose, the legal basis of which is the data subject's express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR</p>	<p>The data will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in all cases, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations</p>

To whom will the data be disclosed?

Eurecat is the main recipient of user data, however, it may be accessible to third parties that develop services to the Data Controller. Those scenarios that required Eurecat service suppliers' access to the user's data, because of the services arranged, shall be submitted to the legal obligations, which are those of article 28 GDPR'S. In any event, Eurecat service suppliers shall not process the user's data for their own or different purposes and shall not overreach from the services purposes, and, in any case, shall not rent, sold, or make it available to third parties.

The Data Controller shall not transfer your data to third parties without your prior consent, which should fulfil the legal requirements.

The Data Controller in case of legal obligations may transfer your data to third parties, without the user prior consent.

The personal data obtained by the web forms may be transferred to certain consortium partners with whom Eurecat cooperate, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact as well as to execute the proper actions to carry out the web form purposes for which the data was given This data access by the consortium partners, does not entail a data assignment for its own purposes. You may consult the detailed list of the project consortium partner here.

Are data transferred internationally?

There are no international data transfers to countries outside the European Union.

What are your rights as a user and how can you exercise them?

Right to access the data

As a user, you can ask us to explain what we do with your personal data. You can also ask us for information about the purpose of the processing of your personal data, the period of time for which we store them, your rights as a user, the transfer of the data to a third country or an international organisation, the existence of automated decisions or profiling on the website, among others.

Right to rectification

If the personal data you have provided to us are inaccurate or incomplete, you are entitled to rectify or supplement them. Please contact us and we will rectify the data according to your request.

Right to restrict the processing

As a user you can request restriction of the processing of your personal data in the following cases:

If you question the accuracy of your personal data, for a period of time that allows us to verify their accuracy.

If the processing is unlawful and you object to the erasure of your personal data, instead of erasure, you request that their use is restricted.

If we no longer need your data for the purposes of processing, but they are needed for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Right to erase

You can request us to erase your personal data immediately. We are obliged to erase the data immediately if they are no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected. In addition, you can ask us to erase your data if you change your mind about the consent you granted, if you object to the processing and there are no justified grounds for it, if your data are processed incorrectly, if the data must be erased in order to comply with a legal obligation or if the data has been obtained related to a legal offer.

Right to information

If you have exercised a right to rectify, erase or restrict your data, we are obliged to inform all the recipients to whom your personal data have been disclosed of such rectification, erasure or restriction of processing, unless this proves impossible or involves a disproportionate effort. As a user, you are entitled to be informed by the data controller about who these recipients are.

Right to data portability

You are entitled to receive the personal data you have provided to us in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format. You are also entitled to transfer this data to another data controller without us being able to prevent this.

Right to object to the data processing

As a user, you are entitled to object to our use of the personal data made available to us at any time for reasons related to your personal situation. We will stop processing your personal data unless we have compelling legitimate grounds to use them, if such grounds override your interests, rights and freedoms or if the processing is for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Right to withdraw the declaration of consent related to data protection

As a user you are entitled to change your declaration of consent related to data protection at any time. This change of decision regarding the consent will not affect the legality of the processing that took place on the basis of the consent provided prior to its withdrawal.

Automated individual decisions, including profiling

You are entitled not to be subject to a decision solely based on automated processing, including profiling, which has legal effects for you or significantly affects you in a similar way.

Right to submit a complaint to a supervisory authority

As a user you are entitled to submit a complaint to a supervisory authority, in particular in the Member State of your residence, place of work or place of infringement, if you consider the processing of your personal data implies a violation of the GDPR.

Where can you exercise your rights?

You can request to exercise your rights at the following e-mail address: legal@eurecat.org

Is it mandatory to provide all the information requested in the data collection forms?

Regarding the forms posted on the website, you must fill in the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal data or only partial completion could mean that Eurecat will be unable to deal with your requests and, therefore, Eurecat will be held harmless for any liability due to not rendering or only partially rendering the requested services.

The personal data provided by the user to Eurecat must be current information so that our records are up to date and error-free. The user is responsible for the veracity of the data provided.

What security measures have we implemented?

Eurecat protects and uses your personal data according to the regulations in force on data protection and information society services.

We have implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures to guarantee the security of the users’ personal data and prevent their alteration, loss, unauthorised processing and/or access thereto, bearing in mind the state of the art, the kind

of data provided and the risks to which they could be exposed, whether due to human action or physical or natural factors, in accordance with the provisions in the regulations in force.

10.2 Legal warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.hypiend.eu is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

Access to the website

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

Use of the website

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third

parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

Operation of the website

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

Liability

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

Policy on links

a) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

b) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

Intellectual and industrial property rights of the content

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names (“distinctive signs”) are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

Applicable legislation

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

Contact

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

10.3 Cookies policy

What are cookies and what are they used for?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user’s device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user’s decisions and habits. Some of the cookies used on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user’s personal data.

What kind of cookies exist?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user’s device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user’s device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user’s device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users’ browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

What kind of cookies does the website use?

The user may be consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, these cookies does not require the user’s agreed neither its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
_pk_id.11.cfba	0	1 year	This cookie is installed by Matomo. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, camapign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies

			store information anonymously and assigns a randomly generated number to identify unique visitors.
_pk_ses.11.cfba	0	30 min	This cookie is installed by Matomo. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, campaign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies store information anonymously and assigns a randomly generated number to identify unique visitors.
cookieLawinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies are used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary".
cookieLawinfo-checkbox-non-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Not Necessary".
test_cookie	0	11 months	Test for GDPR plugin
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and

			<p>is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.</p>
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How do you disable cookies in a browser?

The cookies set up is directly reflected to the browser used, however here are additional information about how the user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending on the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered as a Third-party cookies. For example, in case of user chooses Google’s browser and uses its translate tool of the full website, Google install its own cookies in the user’s computers which are not managed by the website publisher as well as has not liability about them. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#).
- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#).

Further information

Further information about cookies as well as how to block them at www.allaboutcookies.org, www.youronlinechoices.eu. For any questions or comments about this website cookies, shall contact by email to info@eurecat.org as a web publisher or as a web service supplier.